

The Effectiveness of Instagram Social Media as Interactive Marketing for System Provider Companies

Dinny Talita Sari¹;Wiwik Handayani²

Bachelor of Management, Faculty of Economics and Business
Universitas Pembangunan Nasional "Veteran" Jawa Timur Surabaya, Indonesia

Abstract:- Marketing challenges in the digital age have become a paramount focus for system provider companies. These companies seek to promote their technological solutions to an increasingly sophisticated and tech-savvy customer base. To tackle these challenges, system providers are now harnessing Instagram social media as an interactive marketing tool, poised to revolutionize the dynamics of their business. Interactive marketing stands out as a powerful strategy to forge robust relationships between companies and customers. Instagram, equipped with features such as comments, likes, and stories, serves as a platform to enhance audience engagement. The success of interactive marketing on Instagram holds the potential to make a substantial contribution to improving brand image and driving sales. The objective of this study is to pinpoint the variables influencing the effectiveness of interactive marketing through Instagram for system provider companies. Among these variables, content suitability and copywriting emerge as key factors that can heighten interaction. The study encompasses all Instagram social media users across Indonesia. Quantitative data were collected through online surveys. Data analysis in this research used a Structural Equation Model (SEM) approach based on Partial Least Square (PLS) using SMART PLS 4.0 software. The results of the study demonstrate that both content suitability and copywriting exert a significant impact on interaction, underscoring their crucial role in the digital marketing landscape.

Keywords:- Marketing, Social Media, Content Marketing, Copywriting, Social Media Interaction.

I. INTRODUCTION

Digital transformation allows companies to continue to innovate in marketing strategies, with a primary focus on interaction with customers. Marketing is one way for system providers to develop brands and introduce them to a wider audience. Marketing is the process of finding out customer needs and serving those needs profitably. If an organization is obsessed with looking for profits, it will never find them. But if it is focused on satisfying its customers, profits will come automatically (Arun Kumar & N. Meenakshi, 2011). This shows that marketing efforts are not just optional, but a must for any entrepreneur who wants to achieve success in a competitive market. Through proper marketing efforts, businesses can expand market share, create new opportunities, and develop a portfolio of products or services. Marketing is not only about selling products or services to customers, but also about understanding customer needs, wants, and preferences to

provide the right solutions. So it takes interaction with customers directly both online and offline to find out customer needs and wants.

With the development of the digital world, now marketing can also be done digitally and can be accessed anytime and anywhere. One form of digital marketing is the use of social media as a marketing tool. Social media is a very effective marketing tool in today's business world. Social media encourage time and space in business interaction with the potential consumer and create a feel of closeness (Mersey et al., 2010). Social media has proven to be one of the most effective marketing tools in the modern business world. This is because social media provides a variety of benefits that include a wide reach, direct interaction with customers, and flexibility in delivering marketing messages. One of the main features of social media is its ability to support social interaction. Social media users can communicate, share, and interact with each other, which creates a great opportunity for businesses to participate in the dialogue. Social media is supported by internet-based technology that allows access without space and time restrictions. Wise and strategic use of social media can also help companies expand market share, increase brand awareness, and increase customer engagement.

By implementing digital marketing will also realize interactive marketing. In the interactive marketing landscape, marketing can be fun, exciting and inviting, with more active customer participation and engagement (Wang, 2021). Communication not only flows from company to customer, but also from customer to company, the company listens and responds to customer input and needs. The Company also uses customer data and information to present content that is more relevant and appropriate to individual preferences. This allows companies to get closer to customers, increase loyalty, and create more meaningful experiences in marketing and business interactions.

To identify interactive marketing can run effectively there are supporting variables, one of which is content suitability. The content in question is content posted on the social media accounts of the system provider company. Digital content marketing is the management process responsible for identifying, anticipating, and satisfying customer requirements profitably in the context of digital content, or bit-based objects distributed through electronic channels (Rowley, 2008). That way, content in content marketing is not only made haphazardly. Instead, the content is specifically designed, with deep consideration related to the target audience, the message to be conveyed, and the ultimate goal of the marketing campaign. The goal is to encourage interaction to invite readers or viewers to

engage, such as giving likes and comments, sharing content.

In addition to content marketing, another variable is copywriting. The use of copywriting in the content to be posted can support the emergence of interaction so that it can realize interactive marketing. Copywriting provides a direct line of communication between existing and prospective Customers and product or service (Imrul Kayes, 2018). The main purpose of copywriting is to inspire, inform, or influence the audience with carefully selected words. Copywriting has a key role in giving value a deeper meaning, the words used in the text must be able to describe a deep message, value, or story related to the company. Good copywriting also considers the target audience.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Marketing Theory

Marketing is an organizational function and a set of processes for creating, communicating, and delivering value to customers and for managing customer relationships in ways that benefit the organization and its stakeholders (Dorkenoo et al., 2015). Marketing is not just about selling a product or service, but also about understanding the needs and wants of customers and creating value for them. In addition, marketing involves social aspects that involve individuals and groups in society, so it has a wider impact than just commercial transactions. Successful marketing involves a deep understanding of the market, customers, and business environment, as well as the ability to respond to changes and trends in society.

B. The Use of Instagram Social Media in Marketing

Social media is an effective marketing tool because it has a very communicative and interactive nature. Instagram is a powerful marketing channel that brands should be using to its fullest extent. As it stands, Instagram is the right solution for marketing at the right time (Academicians, 2018). Instagram is a very popular social media platform for marketing, especially for businesses and brands.

Because Instagram can share interesting visual content, such as product photos, promotional videos, and stories that showcase the company's brand image. Instagram also offers a variety of ways to interact with followers, including comments, likes, and shares, which can lead to strong communication with the company's customers.

Many business people uses Instagram as their new platform to market their products and services. The functions of Instagram do not only attract the attentions of all the social networkers but also the marketers (Huey & Yazdanifard, 2014). Instagram offers great opportunities for business activities as a means to promote products, services, brands, or content. Instagram is also famous for its focus on visual content such as photos and videos. This provides an opportunity for businesses to showcase products or services in an interesting and creative way, which can attract the attention of potential customers. Instagram also allows businesses to interact directly with customers through comments, direct messages, or responses to posts that can help build a closer relationship with customers.

C. Interactive Marketing

Interactive marketing is a type of marketing activity fostering interaction with targeted market segments in virtual and real-life environment through interaction channels and methods (Sekerin et al., 2018). Interactive marketing refers to a marketing strategy that focuses on two-way interaction between the company and the customer. Involves the use of digital and online technologies to communicate with customers directly and respond to their needs and preferences. Such communication creates active interaction through comments, story responses, critiques and suggestions, or online surveys. Companies can benefit from this customer feedback to improve the product or service.

D. Content Marketing

Visual content not only provides a tantalising visual experience, but also has tremendous capabilities in increasing attraction and conversion (Sunarso & Mustafa, 2023). In the context of visual content creation, it is necessary to pay attention to design elements, layout, colors, and other aesthetic elements to create visually appealing content. But while aesthetics are important, visual content should also convey useful information. This information can be a marketing message, data, facts, or a story that you want to tell your audience.

III. RESEARCH METHOD

A. Research Variables

Research variables are components or factors that are observed, measured, or manipulated in a research study to understand the relationship between existing elements or to answer a research question. These variables are used to collect the necessary data in the analysis and interpretation of research results. In this study entitled "The Effectiveness of Instagram Social Media as Interactive Marketing in System Provider Companies", there are several research variables, consisting of the dependent variable (Y) namely Interaction and the independent variable (X) namely content marketing (X1), copywriting (X2).

Indicators of variable Y (Interaction) are taken from (Fikri, 2018) which consists of 5 indicators, namely:

- Y1 with sub criteria "Like"
- Y2 with sub criteria "Other"
- Y3 with sub criteria "Comments"
- Y4 with sub criteria "Share"
- Y5 with sub criteria "Click"

Indicators of the variable X1 (Content Marketing) are taken from (Milhinhos, 2015) which consists of 6 indicators, namely:

- X1-1 with sub criteria "Relevance"
- X1-2 with sub criteria "Accuracy"
- X1-3 with "Valued" sub criteria
- X1-4 with "Easy to Understand" sub criteria
- X1-5 with sub criteria "Easy to find"
- X1-6 with sub criteria "Consistent"

Indicators of variable X2 (Copywriting) are taken from (Zulkifly & Firdaus, 2014) which consists of 5 indicators, namely:

- X2-1 with sub criteria "Attention"
- X2-2 with sub criteria "Interest"
- X2-3 with sub criteria "Desire"
- X2-4 with sub criteria "Conviction"
- X2-5 with sub criteria "Action"

B. Population and Sample

The population in this study is all Instagram social media users throughout Indonesia. This population includes all individuals or accounts actively using Instagram in Indonesia, including personal users, businesses, organizations, and other entities that use the platform. This population represents the entire group that is the focus of the study.

In this study, the author used a sampling method with a random sampling method. Random sampling is a method in which every member in a population has an equal chance of being part of the sample. In other words, the sample is selected randomly and without bias from a larger population.

C. Data Types and Sources

This type of data in this study uses quantitative data, which means the data is in the form of numbers and can be measured numerically. Quantitative data is used to measure and analyze variables related to the effectiveness of Instagram social media as an interactive marketing tool.

While the data sources used in this study are:

- **Primary Data:** Obtained directly from respondents or research subjects. In this study, primary data were obtained through questionnaires distributed to respondents. The questionnaire is implemented through a Google Form, which allows respondents to fill out the questionnaire online. In the questionnaire, there is a 5-point Likert scale, which is used to measure respondents' attitudes or perceptions of variables relevant to this study.
- **Secondary Data:** Obtained from pre-existing sources, such as document studies, citations, and theoretical studies. In this study, secondary data were used to support and complement the analysis.

➤ Data Collection Methods

In this study, the authors used an online questionnaire with Google Form as a tool to collect data from respondents. The questionnaire was designed using a 5-point Likert scale, which includes five answer choices: strongly disagree (STS), disagree (TS), neutral (N), agree (S), and strongly agree (SS). This scale is used to measure respondents' perceptions or attitudes towards various statements. Then the data obtained will be processed in the SMART PLS 4.0 program as primary data.

IV. RESULTS

A. Validity and Reliability Test

According to (Esposito Vinzi, Chin, Henseler, & Wang, 2010), the reliability of indicators indicates the extent to which the variation in indicators can be explained by latent variables, taking into account the magnitude of the loading values. If the loading value is less than 0.4, then the indicator needs to be removed from the model.

Table 1: Outer Loading Value

Indicator	Copywriting	Interaction	Content Suitability
X1.1			0,637
X1.2			0,626
X1.3			0,709
X1.4			0,624
X1.5			0,787
X1.6			0,784
X2.1	0,708		
X2.2	0,823		
X2.3	0,783		
X2.4	0,684		
X2.5	0,858		
Y1.1		0,639	
Y1.2		0,775	
Y1.3		0,803	
Y1.4		0,750	

Table 3: Composite Reliability Value

Variable	Composite reliability
Content Suitability (X1)	0,811
Copywriting (X2)	0,835
Interaction (Y)	0,825

The indicator in determining whether the variable is reliable or not can be seen in the value of composite reliability. According to (Agus Purwanto & Yuli Sudargini, 2021), the cut point value for composite reliability should be

above 0.7, so variables with composite reliability values exceeding 0.7 can be considered reliable and accepted for further correlation testing between variables.

Table 3: Level of Validity and Correlation Between Variables

Correlation Between Variables	Content Suitability (X1) -> Interaction	Copywriting (X2) -> Interaction
Original sample	0,269	0,522
Sample mean	0,283	0,529
Standard deviation	0,131	0,134
T statistics	2,051	3,893
P values	0,040	0,000

B. Hypothesis Testing

After testing the validity of the correlation between variables and the reliability of each indicator and variable, which have been declared valid and reliable, the next step is to test the correlation between variables by operating the bootstrapping menu in Smart PLS software, considering the P Value. According to (Kock, 2016), a P Value < 0.5 indicates that the hypothesis can be accepted or is significant, and if P Value > 0.5, then the hypothesis cannot be accepted or is not significant.

C. Content Relevance to Interaction

The first hypothesis examines the influence of content relevance variable (X1) on interaction (Y), showing a P Value result of 0.040 < 0.050, which means that content relevance has a significant effect on interaction. If content relevance is increased, it will impact interaction. Thus, the second hypothesis is accepted, indicating a positive influence of content relevance on interaction. Content relevance also plays a crucial role in creating interaction in marketing by ensuring that the conveyed message is relevant, engaging, and meaningful to the target audience. Appropriate content ensures that marketing messages are relevant to the needs, issues, and desires of the audience. If the audience feels that the content provides value or relevant information to them, they are more likely to interact, such as giving feedback or sharing the content. As explained in a study by (Wahyudin & Rokhaminawanti, 2022), it is stated

that it is necessary to increase interesting content to encourage more audience participation by giving likes and comments, ultimately leading the audience to share interesting content with other followers and provide feedback.

D. Copywriting Impact on Interaction

The second hypothesis examines the influence of the copywriting variable (X2) on interaction (Y), showing a P Value result of 0.000 < 0.010, indicating that copywriting significantly affects interaction. If copywriting is enhanced, it will impact interaction. Thus, the first hypothesis is accepted, indicating a positive influence of copywriting on interaction. Copywriting plays a crucial role in creating interaction in marketing due to its ability to capture attention, motivate, and inspire actions from the target audience. Good copywriting can capture the attention of readers or potential audiences from the beginning. With the right and engaging words, copywriting can make people pause to read and understand the message being conveyed. As explained in a study by (Imrul Kayes, 2018), this is where ad copywriting really becomes an art form. To make every word count means that to get rid of the fluff and keep the meaningful words. This makes readers interested and encourages them to take action, such as consistently leaving comments in the comment section of each post. This can also enhance interaction on social media.

Fig. 1: Path Diagram with Loading Factor Values

E. Level of Influence and Effects Between Independent Variables on the Dependent Variable

After obtaining significant results for all hypotheses proposed in this study, the next step is the discussion of the extent of the level of influence and effects between independent variables (X1 & X2) on the dependent variable (Y). The indicator used is f^2 , representing the level of influence of independent variables on the dependent variable, according to (Cohen, 1988), where a value ≥ 0.02 indicates a weak influence, a value ≥ 0.12 indicates a moderate influence, and a value ≥ 0.35 indicates a strong influence. As seen in Figure 1, the correlation between content relevance to interaction has an f^2 value of 0.269, meaning that content relevance has a moderate influence on interaction. Meanwhile, the f^2 value in the correlation between copywriting and interaction is 0.522, indicating that copywriting has a strong influence on interaction.

V. DISCUSSION

- Indicators for Variables X1 (Content Marketing), X2 (Copywriting), and Y1 (Interaction) already have outer loading values above 0.4, thus can be deemed reliable, as explained in Table 1.
- Table 2 shows the composite reliability values for each variable, with respective values for copywriting at 0.835, interaction at 0.825, and content suitability at 0.811. None of the variable values are below 0.7, indicating that the variables can be considered reliable. Therefore, it can be stated that the supporting variables (X1 & X2) for the interaction variable (Y) used in this study have good reliability, allowing for further analysis.
- The results of the correlation test between variables obtained show that these results support the hypotheses proposed earlier, with both hypotheses having P Values of 0.040 and 0.000 (see Table 3).
- The first hypothesis examines the influence of content relevance variable (X1) on interaction (Y), showing a P Value result of $0.040 < 0.050$, which means that content relevance has a significant effect on interaction. If content relevance is increased, it will impact interaction.
- The second hypothesis examines the influence of the copywriting variable (X2) on interaction (Y), showing a P Value result of $0.000 < 0.010$, indicating that copywriting significantly affects interaction. If copywriting is enhanced, it will impact interaction.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results of data analysis and hypotheses testing in this study, it can be concluded that each hypothesis has a significant impact. Hypothesis 1, which is the correlation between X1 (Content Relevance), has a significant effect on Y (Interaction) with a P Value of 0.040 and a moderate effect with an f^2 value of 0.269. Hypothesis 2, which is the correlation between X2 (Copywriting), has a significant effect on Y (Interaction) with a P Value of 0.000 and a strong effect with an f^2 value of 0.522. The highest value is in the second hypothesis, which is the correlation between copywriting and interaction, meaning that the interaction process occurring on the Instagram social media of the system provider company is greatly influenced by

copywriting. The lowest value is in the first hypothesis, which is the correlation between content relevance and interaction. Although it has a significant impact, content relevance still needs improvement to further support copywriting for more optimal interactions on the Instagram social media of the system provider company.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Academician, I. (2018). Advance and Innovative Research. 5(1).
- [2]. Agus Purwanto, & Yuli Sudargini. (2021). Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) Analysis for Social and Management Research : A Literature Review. Journal of Industrial Engineering & Management Research, 2(4), 114–123.
- [3]. Arun Kumar & N. Meenakshi. (2011). Marketing Management, 2nd Edition (2nd ed.). Vikas Publishing.
- [4]. Cohen, J. (1988). Statistical Power Analysis for the Behavioral Sciences (second ed.). Lawrence Erlbaum Associates are printed on acid-free paper, and their bindings are chosen for strength and durability.
- [5]. Dorkenoo, C. B., Nyarko, I. K., Agbemava, E., & Asimah, V. (2015). Marketing public tertiary institutions in Ghana via informative advertising: A study of Ho Polytechnic. International Journal of Advanced Research, 3(11), 211–220.
- [6]. Fikri, K. (2018). Analisis Pengaruh Penggunaan Teks Di Gambar. 11(2), 46–57.
- [7]. Huey, L. S., & Yazdanifard, R. (2014). How Instagram Can Be Used as a Tool in Social Network Marketing Center for Southern New Hampshire University (SNHU) Programs HELP College of Art and Technology Center for Southern New Hampshire University (SNHU). Program HELP College of Art and Technology, September, 1–7. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/265377226%0AHow>
- [8]. Imrul Kayes, S. (2018). Internship report on Impact of Copywriting in Marketing Communication. 1–35.
- [9]. Kock, N. (2016). Hypothesis testing with confidence intervals and P values in PLS-SEM. International Journal of E-Collaboration, 12(3), 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.4018/IJeC.2016070101>
- [10]. Mersey, R. D., Malthouse, E. C., & Calder, B. J. (2010). Engagement with online media. Journal of Media Business Studies, 7(2), 39–56. <https://doi.org/10.1080/16522354.2010.11073506>
- [11]. Milhinhos, P. (2015). The Impact of Content Marketing on Attitudes and Purchase Intentions of Online Shoppers: the Case of Videos & Tutorials and User-Generated Content. Escola Brasileira De Administracao Publica E De Empresas (FGV EBAPE), 1–75.
- [12]. Rowley, J. (2008). Understanding digital content marketing. Journal of Marketing Management, 24(5–6), 517–540. <https://doi.org/10.1362/026725708X325977>
- [13]. Sekerin, V. D., Gorokhova, A. E., Dudin, M. N., Danko, T. P., & Nikolaykin, N. I. (2018). Applying interactive marketing methods to improve the quality of university educational services. Quality - Access to

- Success, 19(163), 37–42.
- [14]. Sunarso, B., & Mustafa, F. (2023). Analysing the Role of Visual Content in Increasing Attraction and Conversion in MSME Digital Marketing. 1(3), 193–200.
- [15]. Wahyudin, & Rokhaminawanti, E. (2022). Strategi Social Media Marketing Pada Akun Instagram Wadezig! Dalam Membangun Brand Awareness. Prosiding FRIMA (Festival Riset Ilmiah Manajemen Dan Akuntansi), 6681(4), 572–580. <https://doi.org/10.55916/frima.v0i4.409>
- [16]. Wang, C. L. (2021). New frontiers and future directions in interactive marketing: Inaugural Editorial. *Journal of Research in Interactive Marketing*, 15(1), 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JRIM-03-2021-270>
- [17]. Zulkifly, H. Z., & Firdaus, N. (2014). Persuasion and the Online Consumers: Investigating Copywriting Strategies in Native Advertisements. *International Journal of Social Science and Humanity*, 4(6), 430–434. <https://doi.org/10.7763/ijssh.2014.v4.393>.